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Introduction

In the ever-evolving landscape of research and scientific exploration, access to state-of-the-art research infrastructures facilitates innovation and knowledge growth in all scientific disciplines.

The European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) defines research infrastructures (RIs) as "facilities, resources, and related services that are used by the scientific community to conduct top-level research in their respective fields. They include: major scientific equipment (or sets of instruments), knowledge-based resources such as collections, archives and scientific data, e-infrastructures, such as data and computing systems and communication networks and any other tools that are essential to achieve excellence in research and innovation".

The overarching goal of RIs is to provide researchers with state-of-the-art tools and capabilities that go beyond individual or institutional capacities. By fostering collaboration and open access, RIs can become catalysts for accelerating scientific progress and international cooperation.

Remote access to RIs allows scientists to interact with and use these important resources without having to be on-site at the institutions. They can do this via web-based platforms, virtualisation technologies and secure network connections, or by shipping samples to an RI to have them analysed. This not only makes it easier for researchers to use state-of-the-art equipment, but also

fosters international partnerships and gives more people access to valuable resources that would otherwise be difficult to access.

Even before the COVID-19 pandemic, European RIs had developed a variety of remote and digital access models tailored to their specific operation modes, associated legal standards and requirements, and available operational resources. The subsequent pandemic acted as a catalyst for the expansion and further development of these remote access models, especially in areas where physical access was predominant.

The eRImote project (European Research Infrastructures - Pathway to Improved Resilience through Digital and Remote Access) was developed in response to the COVID-19 pandemic and the unprecedented speed with which the scientific community responded to provide solutions, highlighting the importance of open science in accelerating innovation. To address these challenges across different scientific domains, the eRImote consortium brings together 12 partners from the environmental, life, physical and social sciences. The consortium seeks to identify strategies and solutions to enable the transition to more remote and digital access to RI services across ESFRI domains.

In this report, we examine the remote access landscape of European RIs and seek to identify existing frameworks for specific requirements for digital/remote access, such as access to sensitive data or authentication and authorization infrastructure (AAI). We also incorporated major discussion items from the eRImote Workshops organised by WP3 in 2022 (cf. to the Annex).

Five Expert Groups were constituted in the beginning of 2023. *Main discussion items and take-aways from these Expert groups will be added to an updated version of the report in early 2024.*

An eRImote working definition of digital and remote access

The European Charter for Access¹ defines access to RIs in the following: "The legitimate and authorised physical, remote and virtual admission to, interactions with and use of research infrastructures and to services offered by Research Infrastructures to Users. Such access can be granted, amongst others, to machine time, computing resources, software, data, data-communication services, trust and authentication services, sample preparation, archives, collections,

¹ European charter of access for research infrastructures: <https://op.europa.eu/de/publication-detail/-/publication/78e87306-48bc-11e6-9c64-01aa75ed71a1/>

the set-up, execution and dismantling of experiments, education and training, expert support and analytical services."

In its White Paper from 2020², ESFRI seeks to further differentiate between physical, virtual and remote access:

Physical Access is "hands-on" access when users physically visit an infrastructure, facility, or equipment. The available services or resources are not unlimited and a competitive process is required following a defined procedure and criteria for selection of users.

Remote Access is access to resources and services offered by the RI without users physically visiting the infrastructure/facility. Similar to physical access, the services or resources are not unlimited and a competitive selection is required.

Virtual Access means free access to users provided through communication networks; the available services or resources can be simultaneously used by an unlimited number of users and the users are not selected. Virtual access typically concerns access to data and digital tools.

The main differentiating criteria for ESFRI are therefore whether or not a physical presence of the user is required and whether or not the number of access units is limited. Both *remote access* and *virtual access* do not require the presence of the user, but they may differ fundamentally in the way users interact with remote resources and in the level of engagement required from RI operational staff. eRImote covers **remote and digital access** and therefore does not make an *a priori* distinction between the remote and virtual categories. Both types of access may be considered as related, but with different operational requirements and limitations that need to be taken into account.

Remote and digital access provision by European RIs

The extent to which remote/digital access is granted varies significantly between RIs, depending also on the type of tools/technical platforms RIs grant access to. The differences were more pronounced before the pandemic, but still exist today.

RIs that mainly support computational or data-driven research, e.g. data archives and digital repositories in various scientific fields, enable the reuse of data previously generated for research or administrative purposes. Very often, these RIs also host large reference databases for specific data

² ESFRI White Paper 2020 - Making Science Happen:

https://www.esfri.eu/sites/default/files/White_paper_ESFRI-final.pdf

types. Examples are CESSDA³, ESS⁴, SOBIGDATA⁵, ELIXIR⁶ or EBRAINS⁷. These types of RIs usually provide predominantly digital/remote access, although there may be profound access restrictions related to data ownership and trust and/or security aspects of certain data types. To some extent this also applies to the so-called *e-infrastructures*, which provide computational resources such as high-performance computing (PRACE⁸) or distributed computing resources (EGI⁹). The data security aspects of digital/remote access provision will be explored in the section 'Access to Sensitive Data' below.

Most RIs provide access to physical resources, from physical materials stored in biorepositories to distributed or centralised scientific instrumentation of varying scales. To the extent that these RIs also provide centralised access to the data generated, digital/remote access may face similar opportunities and limitations as the group of RIs described earlier.

Biorepositories such as BBMRI¹⁰, MIRRI¹¹ or INFRAFRONTIER¹² usually do not require physical user interaction, they rather provide centralised points-of-access to a large number of distributed physical sample collections and associated data (although accessibility may be restricted by security or data privacy aspects).

Fully digital/remote access to instruments is typically set up when, for example, the RI autonomously analyses user-provided samples and then provides the generated data (and associated data analyses), as is the case for the INFRAFRONTIER *Mouse Clinics* or EU-OPENSREEN¹³. Sometimes biosafety requirements prescribe such an operation mode, as in the case of ERINHA¹⁴. Many RIs in the environmental or astronomy field operate observatories/sensor arrays that don't require direct

³ CESSDA - Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives: <https://www.cessda.eu/>

⁴ ESS - European Social Survey: <https://www.europeansocialsurvey.org/>

⁵ SOBIGDATA - The Research Infrastructure for Big Data and Social Mining: <http://www.sobigdata.eu>

⁶ ELIXIR - A distributed infrastructure for life-science information: <https://elixir-europe.org/>

⁷ EBRAINS - Europe's Research Infrastructure for Brain Research: <https://www.ebrains.eu/>

⁸ PRACE - Partnership for Advanced Computing in Europe: <https://prace-ri.eu>

⁹ EGI - Advanced Computing Services for Research: <https://www.egi.eu/>

¹⁰ BBMRI - European Research Infrastructure for Biobanking: (<https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/>)

¹¹ MIRRI – Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure: <https://www.mirri.org/>

¹² INFRAFRONTIER - European Research Infrastructure for Modelling Human Diseases: <https://www.infrafrontier.eu/>

¹³ EU-OPENSREEN - European Research Infrastructure for Chemical Biology: <https://www.eu-openscreen.eu/>

¹⁴ ERINHA - European Research Infrastructure on Highly Pathogenic Agents: <https://erinha.eu/>

user interaction (e.g. EMSO¹⁵, ICOS¹⁶). A special case of digital/remote access is the **remote control of RI instruments** by the user.

Many RIs in the physical and material sciences have a long tradition of providing in-situ access to instrumentation, where users bring and analyse their samples themselves, supported by RI operational staff (e.g. Euro-BioImaging¹⁷, INSTRUCT¹⁸, or the synchrotron radiation and free electron laser user facilities organised in LEAPS¹⁹). This kind of access provision was particularly disrupted by the pandemic, and the RIs had to newly establish or scale up already existing digital/remote access models to replace the usual site visits. Today, most of these RIs provide both, physical and virtual/remote access options, sometimes even to the same kind of instrumentation (e.g. Euro-BioImaging, EMSO, INTERACT²⁰).

eRImote has addressed digital/remote access provision in the *Workshop on Remote operations of RI services and Data and access security* on 24/25 Oct 2022. Major aspects and take-aways related to remote/digital access provision were:

- Users usually need to be specifically trained to access RI resources and services remotely, specifically in cases where physical access was the predominant access model before remote access was established. In addition, remote/digital access often requires also specific training for the RI operators.
- In most cases remote user access requires more input from the RI operational staff compared to direct physical access to RI instrumentation by the users (i.e. higher operational costs).
- Sample preparation, shipping and on-site handling is a real challenge, particularly when potentially hazardous material or live samples are involved. Sample handling may also require a different set of legal documentation, such as Material Transfer Agreements, etc.
- Moving from physical to remote access has led both to increases and to decreases in operational efficiency in different RIs.
- Longer studies may require a hybrid setup between physical and remote access.
- Loss of physical interactions during digital/remote access may lead to a devaluation of the service provision by the users.

¹⁵ EMSO – European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water column Observatory: <https://emso.eu/>

¹⁶ ICOS - Integrated Carbon Observation System: <https://www.icos-cp.eu/>

¹⁷ Euro-Bioimaging - European Research Infrastructure for Biological and Biomedical Imaging: <https://www.eurobioimaging.eu/>

¹⁸ Instruct-ERIC - Structural Biology European Research Infrastructure Consortium: <https://instruct-eric.org/>

¹⁹ LEAPS - League of European Accelerator-based Photon Sources: <https://leaps-initiative.eu/>

²⁰ INTERACT - International Network for Terrestrial Research and Monitoring in the Arctic: <https://eu-interact.org>

Three expert groups deal with best practices and challenges of digital/remote access provision: Expert Group I - Researcher experiences with remote/virtual access, sample handling and quality assurance, Expert Group IV - Remote Instrument control and Expert Group V - International access and accessibility of RI services. The main discussion items and take-aways from these Expert groups will be added to an updated version of the report in early 2024.

Remote training of RI users and operators

The provision of training for RI users and operators is a very important part of the RI activities, for several reasons:

RIs often include complex and specialised equipment, software and facilities. Training ensures that RI operators and users know how to operate these resources efficiently and make the best use of them. Proper training helps to avoid unnecessary errors, reduce downtime and optimise the use of expensive and valuable equipment. RI operation may involve hazardous materials, powerful instruments or sensitive data. Training ensures that operators and users are aware of the safety protocols, security measures and ethical considerations involved.

Proper training improves researchers' skills and knowledge and enables them to conduct high-quality experiments and data analysis. Properly trained users are more likely to produce reliable and reproducible results. Particularly for early career researchers or those new to a particular RI, user training provides a supportive environment to gain hands-on experience.

Finally, training activities enable RI operators to gather valuable feedback from users. Understanding users' needs, challenges and suggestions can help refine and improve the infrastructure's services and capabilities.

Remote training was already gaining traction prior to the pandemic restrictions, due to its obvious advantages: *Increased accessibility and flexibility, reach and inclusivity* as participants can attend from anywhere. *Increased cost efficiency* as travel and accommodation costs are saved for providers and participants. *Recording of training sessions* allows training material to be revisited for consolidation and future reference; the resulting *consistent training content* ensures that all participants receive the same information.

Remote training has, however, also several disadvantages that need to be carefully balanced against the benefits: *Limited hands-on experiences*: Some aspects of research infrastructure training may require hands-on experience that is difficult to replicate remotely. Participants may thus not have sufficient contact with physical equipment or instruments. *Lack of face-to-face interactions*: In remote training, opportunities for immediate feedback and spontaneous discussion are limited. In addition, participants may be distracted in their own environment, which affects engagement.

eRImote has addressed digital/remote access provision in the *Workshop on Remote training for RI users and staff & User interactions and networking in remote/digital service provision* on 21/22 Sep 2022. Major aspects and take-aways related to remote/digital access provision were:

- Remote training delivery is often easier for trainers, but more difficult for trainees (e.g. requires actively approaching the trainer in case of questions, problems, since non-verbal communication is missing).
- Remote training efficiency increases with well-structured content, careful preparation of material, the opportunity to submit questions beforehand or bring use cases.
- Assessing the efficacy of remote training is difficult, active engagement from the trainees is not guaranteed.
- Hybrid training approaches (mix of in-person and remote sessions) are efficient, particularly for longer and more comprehensive training activities. Hybrid solutions usually mean higher effort for setting up the trainings.

A dedicated expert group deal with best practices and challenges of remote training: Expert Group III - Remote training for RI staff and researchers. The main discussion items and take-aways from this Expert group will be added to an updated version of the report in early 2024.

Specific requirements for digital/remote access

Access to sensitive data

The ISO-5127 terminology register²¹ defines sensitive data as "data with potentially harmful effects in the event of disclosure or misuse".

Sensitive data can be **personal data** (data relating to an identified or identifiable individual). Personal data includes information about racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership and data about a person's health or sex life.

Sensitive data also includes **classified information** (data to which access is restricted by administrative means depending on the level of data protection or information protection sought). This may be *data relating to environmental risks* (e.g. nuclear or other sensitive installations) or the protection of the environment (in particular habitats, protected animal and plant species). *Proprietary data* are technical or other types of information controlled by a company or public body to secure its competitive advantage. It could potentially be protected by copyright, patent or trade secret laws. *Dual Use Research of Concern (DURC)* is research data that may provide knowledge, information, products or technologies that could be directly misused to pose a significant threat with

²¹ ISO 5127 2017: <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/fr/#iso:std:iso:5127:ed-2:v1:en>

far-reaching potential consequences to public health and safety, agricultural crops and other plants, animals, the environment, materials or national security.

Personal and sensitive data are also specified in Article 4 of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)²²: “The following personal data is considered ‘sensitive’ and is subject to specific processing conditions: personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs; trade-union membership; genetic data, biometric data processed solely to identify a human being; health-related data; data concerning a person’s sex life or sexual orientation.”

Open Science and FAIR data initiatives like the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) place considerable emphasis on direct access to research data which may conflict with the existing strong legal and ethical constraints for accessing confidential or personal data. To deal with these problems, frameworks for accessing sensitive data for RIs in the life sciences²³ and social sciences²⁴ have been developed. The applicability and practicability of these framework in day-to-day RI operations has yet to be assessed.

eRImote has addressed access to sensitive data in the *Workshop on Remote operations of RI services and Data and access security* on 24/25 Oct 2022. Major aspects and take-aways related to access to sensitive data were:

- Sensitive data may still contain metadata that can be openly shared. There is, however, a fine line between metadata and the data itself.
- Even though high level legal frameworks like GDPR exist, the legal situation for a specific dataset is often unclear and requires detailed legal expertise, particularly when data sharing across jurisdictions is involved.
- So far, there exists almost no cross-discipline discussion forum on data sharing topics.
- RI services should operate under Data Processing Agreements, with no or very limited scope for negotiations, as well as Data Transfer Agreements, supported by university tech transfer/legal departments. Data Transfer Agreements defines access, not ownership of data.

A dedicated expert group deal with best practices and challenges of access to data: Expert Group II - Data sharing, Data access and security. The main discussion items and take-aways from this Expert group will be added to an updated version of the report in early 2024.

²² EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) 2018a: <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-4-gdpr/>

²³ EOSC-Life Requirements for hosting/ distributing and access control for sensitive data: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7037444>

²⁴ SSHOC White Paper on Remote Access to Sensitive Data in the Social Sciences and Humanities. 2021 and beyond: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6719121>

Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI)

AAI stands for "Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure". It is a framework or system that provides mechanisms for verifying the identity (authentication) of users, devices or services and establishing their access rights (authorisation) to specific resources or services within a network or information system. AAI is used by RIs to ensure secure access and protect sensitive data and delicate RI instrumentation from unauthorised access.

Different scientific domains have developed different AAI solutions for RIs (e.g. Life-science Login²⁵, umbrellaID for the photon and neutron sciences²⁶). The Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure Architecture (AAI) Task Force of the EOSC association²⁷ aims to provide a consistent architecture for Authentication, Authorization and Access Control for the EOSC. According to the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda and Multi-Annual Roadmap, this should lead to a "pan-European AAI that will be provided by the National and Regional AAI Federations and which will meet all its requirements"²⁸.

Annex - Related eRImote workshops, activities and Expert Groups

- eRImote Workshop on Remote training for RI users and staff & User interactions and networking in remote/digital service provision, 21/22 Sep 2022
- eRImote Workshop on Remote operations of RI services and Data and access security, 24/25 Oct 2022
- eRImote Workshop on Governance, Policy, Funding, and Impact 26 Apr 2023
- eRImote Survey - Best Practices, Bottlenecks and Challenges of Digital and Remote Access Services of Research Infrastructures – Opened in May 2023, ongoing
- Expert Group I - Researcher experiences with remote/virtual access, sample handling and quality assurance (INTERACT Non-Profit Association (INPA))
- Expert Group II - Data sharing, Data access and security (CESSDA-UKDS and CESSDA-ISSDA)
- Expert Group III - Remote training for RI staff and researchers (Euro-BioImaging)
- Expert Group IV - Remote Instrument control (Euro-BioImaging Bio-Hub)
- Expert Group V - International access and accessibility of RI services (Instruct-ERIC)
- eRImote Use Case - EMSO Marine infrastructures: command and control

²⁵ <https://lifescience-ri.eu/lis-login/>

²⁶ <https://umbrellaid.org>

²⁷ <https://www.eosc.eu/advisory-groups/aai-architecture>

²⁸ https://eosc.eu/sites/default/files/2023-01/MAR_2025-27_draft.pdf

- eRImote Use Case - Euro-Biolmaging: entire pipeline of full remote user projects supported by physical access core facilities in the life sciences
- eRImote Use Case - LEAPS: educational format and tool
- eRImote Use Case - INTERACT: collaboration with local communities
- eRImote Use Case - INSTRUCT: practical processes to improve remote service offers and remote project tracking in ARIA

